

NOTES

Infra-red Spectral Studies of Potassium Monohydroxytrifluoroborate

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Travers and Malaprade¹ isolated a salt from mixtures of potassium bifluoride and boric acid, and from chemical analyses ascribed to it the formula $K_2B_2F_6 \cdot 1.5 H_2O$. Later on the same salt has, however, been formulated by Wamser², Ryss³ and Slutskaya, and Pawlenko⁴ as $KBF_3 OH$. In order to decide about the correct formula of the above compound the present authors have undertaken an infra-red study of the above compound.

The above potassium salt was prepared according to Pawlenko⁴, and the IR -spectra was taken in KBr in a Perkin-Elmer apparatus. The compound showed sharp peaks at 755 cm^{-1} and 800 cm^{-1} , and flat strong absorption bands in the region $910\text{-}1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1100\text{-}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3400\text{-}3480\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The IR-spectra of KBF_4 and H_3BO_3 have also been recorded under the same conditions as $KBF_3 OH$. Potassium tetra fluoroborate shows sharp peak at 770 cm^{-1} , a weak one at 1300 cm^{-1} and a band at $1010\text{-}1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Boric acid shows sharp peaks at 880 cm^{-1} , 1190 cm^{-1} , 2260 cm^{-1} , weaker ones at 640 cm^{-1} , 2350 cm^{-1} , and bands at $750\text{-}820\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1370\text{-}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3180\text{-}3240\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

A comparison of these data thus show conclusively the absence of water in the above trifluoroborate, but proves the presence of B-OH bond in it. (The H-OH band⁵ occurs near 1630 cm^{-1} and M-OH band⁵ appears at $3500\text{-}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Thus the formulation of the above compound as the hydroxyfluoroborate was found to be correct.

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